

Peace Education and Violent Behaviour among Students in the University of Calabar, Cross River State-Nigeria

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Okey, Stella-Maris *

ABSTRACT

This study investigated peace education and violent behaviour among students of the University of Calabar, in Cross River State of Nigeria. The population of the study consisted of all undergraduate students of the University of Calabar, Cross River State. Accidental random sampling technique was used to select 400 respondents. A structured Peace Education and Violent Behaviour Questionnaire (PEVBQ) was used to collect data from the respondents. The instrument was tested and the reliability estimate of .83 was obtained. Two (2) research hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and Pearson Product Moment Correlation technique was used to test the hypotheses. The result obtained revealed that values orientation and self-discipline significantly influence violent behaviour. Based on the findings, it was recommended largely that government should make it a policy for peace education to be taught at all levels of our school system to inculcate acceptable and healthier societal values among children and youths. This will ensure the Integration of understanding of peace, human rights, social justice and global issues throughout the curriculum.

INTRODUCTION

Crime and violence among undergraduate students have become synonymous with the Nigerian educational system. Conflict today has become part of organizations. This is more so in an organization as a university with a structure that allows two or more units or groups to share functional boundaries in achieving its set objectives. In universities, people with differing nature -students, lecturers and administrative staff - have to work harmoniously together. Hence, the organizational structure is such that staff and staff, students and students, and staff and students share functional boundaries of exchange of knowledge (Ndum and Okey, 2013).

All over the world, institutions of higher learning have often been regarded as citadel of learning. It is unfortunate that our higher institutions that should be centres of learning have become centres of violence. The situation is that from the Universities to the Polytechnics, to the Colleges of Education and even secondary schools, come stories of violence, torture and unwanted intimidations meted on innocent students on daily basis (Eneji, in Ubi, Abang and Atibu, 2017). To address this culture of violence and aggression in our tertiary institutions, peace education is therefore needed to inculcate values, discipline and well-coordinated behaviour in our students. According to Gumut in Ubi, Abang and Atibu (2017) peace education is the deliberate attempt to educate children and adults in the dynamics of conflict and the promotion of peace making skills, using all the channels and instruments of socialization. Gumut believed that peace education is an investment in the younger generation and by educating the younger minds in the virtues of peace, the skill of conflict analysis and management identification of conflict and source of conflict, a better peaceful future could be secured for humanity. Through peace education students should be taught to suppress their instinctive nature of being violent and instead acquire the virtues of values orientation, self-discipline and peace-building

* Okey, Stella-Maris (Ph.D) Faculty of Education, Department of Educational Management, Cross River University of Technology, Cross River State, Calabar/ NIGERIA

behaviour. This will enhance a conducive academic environment and a less stressful administration.

Onwubiko (2002) remarked that values orientation is an essential part of peace education necessary for all levels of education. Houts, in Ubi, Abang and Atibu (2017) reported that our values, whether explicit or implicit predisposes us to prefer one choice over another, whether in moral judgment decision or any other area of life. Ubom, (2003) opined that most of the time, we attempt to make our actions correspond to our values. If we do not succeed, we must then either change our values or suffer from guilty feelings.

One of the characteristics of an educated man is self-discipline. According to Igwe, in Ubi, Abang and Atibu (2017) discipline is a social training which students should be made to acquire especially during their transitional period from childhood. This training is essential to prepare them for the roles, which they are expected to play as adult members of their communities. Ubom (2003) added that such training is to instil in them a sense of maturity in the role areas of sex, social values, emotional behaviour intellectual activities, moral values judgment and economic activities. Positive goal-setting is an index of peace education. Self-goal setting is the interest, ideal, goals and ambitions of a particular individual. The acquisition of positive goals setting makes an individual to direct his energy toward a course and to achieve self-development and satisfaction. It makes an individual to be motivated to work hard in order to achieve a set goal. Peace education is one means of bringing about national awakening of humanistic, aesthetic and ethical values which are the precondition for peace in individual family, society, national and international life (Konteh, 2009).

Quality and peace education is a human right that should be accorded to all human beings solely by reason of being human. The relationship between peace education and development is well established such that education is a key index of development. Involvement in peace education improves productivity, health and reduces negative features of life such as child labour as well as bringing about empowerment. Peace education opens the door for all citizens to participate in development activities and when citizens are denied this kind of education, they are excluded from the development process, which in turn puts them at a disadvantage vis-à-vis their compatriots with the benefit of education (Ndum and Okey, 2013).

Strategies for achieving peace fall under three basic categories: peacekeeping, peacemaking, and peace-building. Peacekeeping generally involves police or military action and strives to achieve peace through strength and force. Peacemaking involves communication skills like conflict resolution and mediation strategies for interacting non-violently with others. Both of these categories are reactive approaches that kick in after a violent incident has occurred. Peace-building, on the other hand, is a more proactive approach that uses peace education as a means of creating a more stable and peaceful culture, thereby preventing violent incidents from occurring. Peace education is critical to creating a culture that reduces the need for peacemaking and peacekeeping by developing a comprehensive program that teaches people how to interact with others and avoid unnecessary aggression. Let's look at the objectives typically found in peace education. The goals of peace education rely on the assumption that while violent conflict is unavoidable, there is a process by which we can address conflict and minimize violence. Peace education seeks to reduce violence and promote peace-building using the identified objectives to inform the instruction (McGuire, 2020).

As there are many impediments to a culture of peace and non-violence it will take great efforts to achieve the same. It can be achieved through collaborative efforts between families, colleagues, neighbours, classmates, governments and all other people in our world. Everyone can be involved in creating a culture of peace; even if in a minor way, there can be a major impact. If peace is achieved in all of our families there would be positive consequences of this seen in our societies, which would continue to extend throughout our world. If peace is reached in our schools and classrooms and children can extend a peaceful way of living into society, we will see the leaders of our world develop into individuals who understand how to resolve conflicts, have respect for other people and lifestyles, and who work towards the alleviation of poverty while contributing to a peaceful, productive, society.

No meaningful progress can be made in a society devoid of violence and insecurity. This is applicable to our tertiary institutions which are now plagued by violence emanating from cultism and other

violent activities, hence the need for peace education that would engender violence-free school system.

Statement of the Problem

Our tertiary institutions today have been characterized by unavoidable dimensions of violence and upheaval. It has been observed that the atmosphere prevailing in our tertiary institutions provide an inspiring environment for violence to thrive. This may include lack of virile student unionism, erosion of the traditional academic culture, absence of intellectual debates and all other activities that are components of traditional campus culture. Violence does not give room for a stable academic year. Many a time, Universities and other Tertiary Institutions are shot down as a result of one form of violence or the other characterized by wanton destruction of properties to the general break dawn of law and order.

As Gimba (2002) has observed, university students and unemployed graduates earn so much money by taking part in crime related services and contracts which their certificates would not fetch them. Apart from the violent environment to which students have been exposed to, the modern family has failed woefully in deflecting or neutralizing peer group influences which may involve cultist activities.

Indiscipline is central to the factors contributing to the fast dwindling, deteriorating and declining educational standard. The various acts of indiscipline commonly perpetrated by students such as truancy, stealing, hooliganism, examination malpractice, sexual violence and cultism among others are all destructive to the educational system and as such impede the pace of societal development. According to Ndum and Onukwugha (2013), there is no well-tailored educational guidance and counselling process of assisting students achieve the self-understanding and self-direction necessary to make informed decisions and move toward the achievement of their individual objectives devoid of violence.

This paper is focused on peace education and violent behaviour among students in the university of Calabar. It is hoped that the introduction of peace education at all levels of our educational system would inculcate on our students, value orientation and self-discipline attributes that will enable them to live in peace and contribute to national development.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to examine the influence of peace education on violent behaviour among students in the University of Calabar.

Specifically, the study sought to:

- i. Determine the extent to which value orientation influence the incidence of violent behaviour among students in the university of Calabar, Cross River, Nigeria.
- ii. Examine the influence of self-discipline on violent behaviour among students in the university of Calabar, in Cross River, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- i. To what extent does value orientation influence violent behaviour among students of university of Calabar in Cross River State, Nigeria?
- ii. Is there any relationship between self-discipline and violent behaviour among students of the University of Calabar in Cross River State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The study was guided by the following hypotheses:

- i. There is no significant relationship between value orientation and violent behaviour among students of the university of Calabar in Cross River State, Nigeria.
- ii. There is no significant relationship between self-discipline and violent behaviour among

students of the university of Calabar in Cross River State, Nigeria

Method

The population of the study was made of students drawn from University of Calabar, Cross River State. Accidental random sampling technique was adopted to select a total of four hundred (400) respondents made up of 260 male students and 140 female students to form the sample of the study.

A structured Peace Education and Violent Behaviour Questionnaire (PEVBQ) was used to collect data for the study. The questionnaire consisted of section A and B. Section A sought information on personal data such as sex, class and age, while section B consisted of 16 question items which elicited information on value orientation, self-discipline and tendencies for violent behaviour. The instrument employed a 4-point Likert response scale of strongly agreed (SA) Agree (A), Disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD). For positive items, (SA) attracted 4 points, (A) 3 points, (D) 2 point and (SD) 1 point. While on the negative items, (SD) carried 4 points; (D) 3 points (A) 2 points and (SA) 1 point.

Results

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between value orientation and violent behaviour among university of Calabar students in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Table 1: Showing the Analysis of Person Product Moment Correlation of the Relationship between Values Orientation and Violent Behaviour (n=400)

Variable	$\sum x$	$\sum x^2$
	$\sum xy$	r_{xy}
	$\sum y$	$\sum y^2$
Value orientation (x)	13522	365566
	398166	- 316
Violent behaviour (x)	15205	430855

*Significant at .05; df 398; critical r=0884

From the analysis on Table 1 it can be observed that there is negative significant relationship between value orientation and the incidence of violent behaviour among university of Calabar students in Cross River State, Nigeria. This shows that the higher the measure of values orientation the lower the incidence of violent behaviour among students.

Ho2 : There is no significant relationship between self -discipline and violent behaviour among university of Calabar students in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Table 2: Showing the Analysis of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the Relationship between Self- Discipline and Violent Behaviour. (n=400)

Variable	$\sum x$	$\sum x^2$
	$\sum xy$	r_{xy}
	$\sum y$	$\sum y^2$
Self discipline (x)	12726	288011
	351394	-296
Violent behaviour (x)	15206	430855

*Significant at .05; df 398, critical r=0884

The analysis in Table 2 shows that there is a negative significant relationship between self-discipline and violent behaviour among students implying that the higher the measure of self-discipline the lower the incidence of violent behaviour.

Discussion

The analysis in Table 1 showed that there is a negative relationship between value orientation and incidence of violent behaviour among students in tertiary institutions. This implies that the higher the level of values orientation, the lower the incidence of violence behaviour among students. This finding supported Gumnts (2009) position that peace education facilitates the achievement of peace and related sets of social values, largely through learning to recognize, confront and practice alternative forms of violence. This result indicates that students who receive orientation on values will desist from violent behaviours while those without the inculcation of acceptable and health values will exhibit their brute, dangerous, criminal and violent behaviours in school and outside the school.

The result of the analysis on Table 2 revealed that there is a negative significant relationship between self-discipline and violent behaviour among students. This shows that the higher the level of self-discipline of an individual, the lower his propensity to violent behaviour. This finding corroborated with Albert (2001) who maintained that discipline is very necessary for the attainment of peace. He believed that self-discipline affects our responses to conflict and the way we look at and do certain things. Students should have the sense of worth for their own lives and that of others. Do unto others as you would want them to do to you, is the Golden Rule. Self-discipline entails the ability to control one's emotion, passion, anger and respect for others. More emphasis must therefore be placed on character building, responsible leadership and citizenship (Adewale, 2005).

Conclusion

Peace education is imperative not only for the sustainability of our national transformation agenda but also for economic development of Nigeria. This is because peace education sets out to let people see that we do have choices to every action to enable us all to live in harmony with one another. People cannot remain passive to achieve peace, but active participation in the quest for peace. Therefore, formal peace education in our education system is a sure way out for schools to produce acceptable products found worthy in character and in learning.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study the following recommendations were made:

- i. Government should make it a policy for peace education to be taught at all levels of our school system to inculcate acceptable and healthier societal values among children and youths. This will ensure the Integration of understanding of peace, human rights, social justice and global issues throughout the curriculum.
- ii. Develop a climate that models peaceful and respectful behaviour among all members of the learning communities.
- iii. Students who exhibit indiscipline and promote violence and other maladaptive behaviours should be prosecuted accordingly to serve as deterrent to others.

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